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Digital Place Branding for Coffee Ecotourism in West Lampung

ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the conditions and prospective characteristics of the Kopi Rigis tourist village. The investigation was carried out in Rigis Jaya Village, Air Hitam District, West Lampung Regency. It was considered as one of the tourist villages in the district of West Lampung, the location of the study was chosen for a purpose. This research employs a qualitative method. According to the source, the data utilized in this study are either primary or secondary. Observations, interviews, and documenting procedures are used for data collection. The results indicate that Kampung Kopi Rigis is proficient at its branding operations. Kampung Kopi Rigis leverages internet media such as websites, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook in the promotion of tourism spots. However, it is quite regrettable that the website belonging to Kampung Kopi Rigis is not being used adequately for promotional purposes. This is demonstrated by the website's broken features. In addition, this Rigis Coffee Village can be transformed into a sustainable tourist attraction by maximizing and balancing the economic, social and environmental values of its components.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, Tourism Destination Branding, Coffee Ecotourism

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, cities have sought novel methods of self-promotion. Due to rapid advances in technology and shifts from local to global surroundings, cities are compelled to compete to become attractive tourist attractions, sites of employment, and culturally diverse locales (Riza et al., 2012). Each region must have its own brand, similar to a product. Branding enables stakeholders, including people, government, businesses, investors, and other local governments, to comprehend a region's orientation and development strategies and act appropriately. Branding is a tool that facilitates the participation of several stakeholders in the development of a region. They can observe, oversee, and respond to regional development policies and directions. Regional branding

is an important marketing technique and may play a crucial role in bringing stakeholders together by defining the destination's basic values and underlining the necessity for a market orientation.

A brand is an 'identifiable product, service, person, or location that has been enhanced such that the buyer or user perceives relevant and unique additional value that best meets their needs. Numerous professionals have conducted research on the definition of regional branding. Like Branding is an essential element of marketing strategy. Establishing a strong brand perception is vital for a company's success. Through branding initiatives, organizations attract and retain customers by promoting value, image, prestige, or lifestyle (Kemp et al., 2012). The concept of place branding can be traced back to place promotion initiatives, which serve as a central component of place marketing, especially in the tourism environment (Kaplan et al., 2010). Given the importance of branding to regions, the purpose of this study is to analyze branding and its regional applications.

The objective of this study is to identify the conditions and prospective characteristics of the Kopi Rigis tourist village region in relation to the continuing branding process and solutions to further development issues, so that the advantages can be realized more fully.

RESEARCH METHOD

The location of the research is Rigis Jaya Village, Air Hitam District, West Lampung Regency. Considering that Rigis Jaya village is one of the tourist villages in the district of West Lampung, the location of the study was chosen on purpose. This study was done between August and December of 2022.

This form of research employs a qualitative, descriptive methodology. According on the source, the data utilized in this study are either primary or secondary. A primary survey was conducted to support the validity of the secondary data acquired, particularly the description of the supporting

infrastructure for the study of tourist branding schemes in the Rigis coffee tourism village area of West Lampung. In the meantime, secondary data were gathered through analyses of relevant literature, including journals, periodicals, the Rigis Coffee Village website, and other sources pertinent to the issues addressed in this study. Observation, interviews, and documenting procedures are utilized for data collection.

In the development of tourist destinations, the process of branding must prioritize the concept of strength as the primary asset for establishing tourist destination branding. Following is an explanation of the notion of establishing destination branding that focuses on the fundamental point, namely strength.

Brand Culture is the manner in which a Destination Brand can reflect the qualities of a destination based on the cultural components of the local community by highlighting cultural values that develop in the associated tourist destination area. Brand Character is a promise and the intention and final objective of the destination in relation to the brand character that will be developed; this branding often investigates brand character through the following studies: Sincerity, Integrity, and Faith.

Brand Personality is how a destination is compared to a person's personality in everyday life; e.g., down-to-earth, upbeat, imaginative, upscale, daring, etc. Brand Name is a place's identifier or nickname, which will be the primary marketing tool for the destination. Typically, the original name of the tourism area is used when naming the destination, allowing the destination branding process to function best. Brand Logos (and Symbols) are how the location has a marketing-friendly phrase. Slogans can be utilized as a selling factor for a tourist site, with a phrase allowing branding to operate as envisioned.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

West Lampung Regency has a total population of 290,388 people, comprised of 154,414 males and 135,975 women living in 15 subdistricts. West

Lampung Regency has a great tourism potential due to its magnificent natural scenery, which encourages people to visit (Lestari et al, 2022). According to the Regional Tourism Development Master Plan (RIPPDA), West Lampung Regency has a tourism potential of 77 tourist destinations, including 14 Religious Tourism objects, 6 Cultural Tourism objects, 4 Lake Tourism objects, 23 Nature Tourism objects, 18 Historical Tourism objects, 5 Agro-tourism objects, 3 Artificial Tourism objects, and 5 Nature Reserve Tourism objects (Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of West Lampung Regency, 2021). In accordance with the Minister of Agriculture's Decree No. 46/KTSP/PD.300/1/2015 concerning national plantation areas, which designated West Lampung Regency as one of the national plantation areas in Lampung Province, coffee productivity in West Lampung continues to increase. Considering the growing potential of coffee in West Lampung, Rgis Jaya Village could become a potential tourist destination.

West Lampung's Rgis Jaya Hamlet is one of the villages with the potential to serve as a tourist village. Rgis Jaya Village is situated in the region of West Lampung, whereas Pekon Rgis Jaya Tourism Village is situated in the Air Hitam District. A Decree (SK) signed by Mr. Zulkifli Hasan, the head of the Indonesian People's Consultative Assembly, recognized Rgis Jaya Village as a Coffee Tourism Village in 2018. Before being designated as Kampung Kopi Tourism Village, Rgis Jaya Village lagged behind other villages in a number of aspects, such as community activities. However, after being designated as a Tourism Village, there were many changes and improvements in a number of ways, beginning with facilities and infrastructure in agriculture, plantations, as well as human resources for coffee processing beginning with sowing, maintenance, harvesting, and various coffee products to threshing. With the addition of the Rgis Jaya Tourism Village, the overall income of the populace can rise.

Kampung Kopi Rgis Jaya Tourism Village is one of the villages representing Lampung in the 2021 activities for the Indonesian Tourism Village Award organized by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy. In this competition, Kampung Kopi Rgis Jaya Tourism Village was awarded third place for Pioneering Tourism Village.

Description of Rigis Coffee Village Agro-tourism

As the top coffee producer in West Lampung, Kampung Kopi Rigis provides an opportunity to learn more about coffee, beginning with its seeding, cultivation, post-harvest processing, roasting, and brewing, all the way to a ready-to-drink cup. Kampung Kopi Rigis is outfitted with comfortable platforms and views of a broad area of coffee plantations so that it can become a tourist attraction. The indicators for the placement and development of agro-tourism based tourism in Rigis Coffee Village, as described by Lestari (2021: 33), are as follows:

- Unspoiled natural resources with a rural atmosphere have the potential to be a tourist destination.
- The availability of suitable amenities and infrastructure, as well as Pekon Rigis Jaya's strategic location and proximity to the main road.
- The Pekon Rigis Jaya community is accessible, and government and community economic institutions are present.
- Economically and socially, the residents of Pekon Rigis Jaya are motivated to create agro-tourism in the coffee hamlet.
- At Pekon Rigis Jaya, the production of superior commodities continues.

Moreover, Lestari (2021:33) states that the development of agro-tourism in Rigis Jaya Coffee Village serves the following objectives:

1. Perform different development functions, including the development of human resources, institutions, and materials.
2. Protect the natural resources and ecosystem of Pekon Rigis Jaya's most important crop, coffee plantations.
3. Protect the local community's social and cultural life.
4. Develop the tourism industry, which relies on the plantation industry as its primary symbol.
5. Utilizing the potential resources available in Pekon to encourage locals to conduct business.

Online Promotion Mix at Rigis Coffee Village

In doing its online promotion, Kampung Kopi Rigis utilizes a range of digital media, including:

- Website: <https://kampungkopirigis.com/>
- WhatsApp Instagram: @kampoengkopi rigis
- Facebook: Kampong Kopi

To attract more tourists, the manager of the Kampung Kopi Rigis tourist village promotes this attraction via a website accessible at <https://kampungkopirigis.com>. Through this website, potential travelers may readily obtain a variety of information, including the location of tourist locations, the items they sell, business hours, contact information, images of Rigis Coffee Village, etc.

Picture 1

Display of the Main Page of the Rigis Coffee Village Website

Source: Processed by Researchers (2022)

The homepage of Kampung Kopi Rigis also features testimonials from tourists discussing their impressions of the location. This is a type of E-WoM (Electronic Word of Mouth). The trust that potential tourists have in Kampung

Kopi Rigis can be bolstered by the opinions of previous guests through the use of testimonials.

The bottom of the Kampung Kopi Rigis homepage contains contact information including social media profiles (Facebook, Google+, and Instagram), email address, and telephone number. However, none of the social media listed on the website are accessible to visitors.

In the product part of the Rigis Coffee Village website, users can view a variety of coffee and merchandise items alongside images, price tags, and ordering icons. On the website of Rigis Coffee Village, however, the price indicated for each product is Rp 0 rather than the actual price. In addition, none of the Kampung Kopi Rigis products feature a functioning ordering icon.

Picture 2

Display of Kampung Kopi Rigis products on the website

Source: Processed by Researchers (2022)

Rigis Coffee Village Products

Coffee Education

Rigis Jaya Tourism Village offers packages for learning more about coffee. Tourists are encouraged to witness the coffee's journey from upstream to

downstream. Participation in this educational program begins at IDR 150,000. Tourists can observe the entire process, from planting to cultivation to post-harvest processing to roasting and brewing, until the coffee is ready to be consumed. By interacting directly with farmers, this activity allows tourists to have fresh experiences. They will also be armed with knowledge of the various types of coffee, be familiar with the flavor of coffee, and be able to appreciate a cup of coffee brewed according to its own method.

Rigis Robusta Coffee Products

Rigis Coffee is comprised of coffee beans harvested from one of the finest estates in West Lampung Regency (Kampoeng Kopi Rigis Jaya) and processed hygienically by the hands of trained professionals. So that it provides a particular flavor and can satisfy Indonesian coffee enthusiasts. Rigis Jaya Village sells authentic coffee to tourists, including Premium Rigis Coffee with pricing beginning at IDR 20,000 and Red Picks of Rigis Coffee with prices beginning at IDR 25,000. Robusta Coffee (Premium Fine Coffee 200 grams), Robusta Coffee (150 grams Premium), Robusta Coffee (150 grams of Red Picks), Robusta Coffee (200 grams Premium), and Robusta Coffee are produced at Rigis Coffee Kampoeng (150 grams of Red Picks). Red (200 grams), Palm Ants Sugar (250 grams), Robusta Coffee (200 grams Full Wash), and Robusta Coffee (200 grams Full Wash) (Wine 200 grams). In addition to coffee items, Kampoeng Kopi Rigis Jaya sells a variety of merchandise, such as Rigis coffee cups, type 2 t-shirts, and type 1 t-shirts.

Luna Maya package

In the midst of Pekon Rigis Jaya's expansive coffee estates, guests can learn more about coffee while touring the garden. Beginning with the nursery, followed by upkeep, processing, and brewing. Then you may also observe the classic coffee roasting, grinding, and brewing processes. Aside from that, the Rigis Jaya tourism village produces unique culinary items from prospective plantations, such the GARAGAS banana. Then, tourists may feel what it's like to be a coffee farmer and savor the BANCAAN /KEPUNGAN delicacies that are typical of rural areas. This package has beginning prices of IDR 75,000.

Rigis Jaya Coffee in the Perspective of Sustainability Tourism

Economic Aspect

Rigis Jaya Village's economy is supported by the coffee plantation sector of agriculture. The area of coffee plantations in Rigis Jaya Village is approximately 498.34 hectares, and each hectare is capable of producing 2 tons of coffee; therefore, Rigis Jaya Village can produce less than 1,058 tons of coffee per year. The high number of coffee harvests in Rigis Jaya Village is a result of the surrounding community's effective management of coffee plantations. Despite the fact that coffee can only be harvested once a year, the people of Rigis Jaya Village rely on income from other types of plants to sustain their economy. Chili, pepper, banana, jengkol, and other plants are typically utilized by the villagers of Rigis Jaya hamlet to sustain their income (Kemenparekraf, 2021).

Rigis Jaya Village is regarded as one of the top tourist villages that offer educational tours and agro-tourism due to its breathtaking natural beauty, good plantation management by the local community, and government backing. One of tourism's tasks in sustainable development is to reduce poverty. The notion of sustainable tourism in Kopi Rigis Jaya village is exemplified by a rise in the local economy, which directly benefits the residents of Rigis Jaya Coffee village. Using the principle of inclusive development, the establishment of Kampung Kopi Agro-tourism has altered the perspectives of the Pekon Rigis Jaya residents. The community was initially hesitant to contribute to the management of Kampung Kopi Agro-tourism, but after receiving guidance and training, the community gradually began to contribute to the growth of Kampung Kopi Agro-tourism.

Social Aspect

Community intervention is essential to the success of the sustainable tourist development process; thus, it plays an important part in the sustainable process. Not only the government, but the entire society is affected by tourism development, regardless of background. The community's willingness to participate and be accountable for their commitments influences the development process to reach shared objectives.

Community participation in the process of building Kampung Kopi Agro-tourism is evidence that this concept has been successfully implemented. Prior to the emergence of agro-tourism in Kampong Kopi, the majority of Pekon Rigin Jaya residents were unfamiliar with the tourism industry and tourist villages. However, as a result of the development of agro-tourism in Kampung Kopi, the residents of Kampung Kopi Rigin Jaya are slowly beginning to comprehend the tourism industry and the tourist villages that support it in order to enhance the common welfare. The provision of human resources and training in the administration of Kampung Kopi agro-tourism is the most crucial phase since it is the key to the successful development of tourism.

Environmental Aspect

The notion of ecotourism and sustainable travel has been adopted effectively. This is evident by the placement of signs urging tourists to maintain cleanliness at all times and the availability of garbage cans at each tourist attraction. In addition, in order to preserve the Rigin Jaya Coffee Village tourist attraction, there are stalls selling regional items surrounding the site.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reveal that Kampung Kopi Rigin performs its branding operations quite well. Kampung Kopi Rigin leverages internet media such as websites, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook in the promotion of tourism spots. However, it is quite regrettable that the website belonging to Kampung Kopi Rigin is not adequately utilized for promotional purposes. This is demonstrated by the website's broken features. In addition, this Rigin Coffee Village can be transformed into a sustainable tourist attraction by maximizing and balancing the economic, social, and environmental value of its components. Future academics are expected to be able to explore sustainable tourism from an economic, social, and environmental perspective in more depth as a result of suggestions that might be made regarding this study.

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